

Implementation and analysis of temperature and gas sensor datalogger in multi-stage condenser pyrolysis

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 3, 2024

Revised Oct 1, 2024

Accepted Oct 7, 2024

Keywords:

Arduino mega

Condenser

Datalogger

Gas sensor

Pyrolysis

Thermocouple

ABSTRACT

The development of alternative energy sources is crucial for addressing contemporary energy and environmental challenges. This study presents the implementation and analysis of a temperature and gas sensor datalogger within a multi-stage condenser pyrolysis system, designed to assess the potential of pyrolytic liquid smoke derived from *Cerbera odollam* (bintaro) fruit waste. The datalogger system was developed to continuously capture and retain data on temperature, air humidity, and non-condensable gases throughout the pyrolysis process. The experimental research focused on evaluating the impact of varying reactor temperatures (250 °C, 300 °C, and 350 °C) and cooling fluid flow rates on the performance of the condenser and the production of bio-oil. Results indicated that reactor temperature significantly affects bio-oil yield, with the highest output of 190 mL obtained at 350 °C. Additionally, the temperature of the smoke entering each condenser and the cooling water's temperature were found to influence the composition of the condensates produced by each stage. This study highlights the importance of integrating sensor technologies to optimize pyrolysis conditions, thereby enhancing the efficiency of energy production from bintaro fruit waste.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The use of biomass as an alternative energy source [1] is increasingly receiving significant attention in an effort to reduce dependence on fossil fuels [2] and reduce negative impacts on the environment [3]. The biomass pyrolysis process is a promising technology for converting biomass into value-added products such as biochar [4], bio-oil and bio gas [5]. However, monitoring and in-depth understanding of the pyrolysis process is the key to increasing the efficiency and quality of the products produced.

Biomass pyrolysis is a thermochemical process in which biomass materials [6], such as wood, straw, agricultural waste [3], or other organic waste such as bintaro fruit (*Cerbera odollam*) [7] as seen in Figure 1, are heated in the absence of oxygen or with very limited amounts of oxygen. This process produces gas, liquid and solid products [8]. The gas produced consists of a mixture of hydrogen [9], carbon monoxide, methane and other hydrocarbons, while the liquid produced usually consists of a mixture of bio-oil and bio-tar, as well as solids such as charcoal or biomass coke.

Figure 1. *Cerbera odollam* Gaertn

Recent experimental investigations have focused on the separation of groups of target compounds as bio-oil fractions [10]. The condensation temperature range is determined based on the dew point of certain organic groups, thereby allowing for selective and physical separation between each fraction [11]. Controlling the nitrogen flow and narrowing the cooling temperature are key features to maximize liquid recovery.

Although there has been a lot of research carried out in the field of biomass pyrolysis, most of it focuses on the kinetics of the reaction and analysis of the final product, without paying attention in detail to the heat transfer process and the appearance of gas or smoke during the process. Limited direct supervision of the pyrolysis process causes gaps in a comprehensive understanding of the mechanism of pyrolysis. Previous research tends to rely on mathematical models that require complete and accurate experimental data. Therefore, this research aims to fill this gap by utilizing an integrated datalogger system and sensors in an effective manner.

Using a datalogger system with appropriate sensors is an important step in monitoring and recording key parameters during the pyrolysis process. This research has very important relevance because it can provide a deeper understanding of the biomass pyrolysis process, especially in terms of heat transfer and gas or smoke formation. By monitoring the process directly using a datalogger system and appropriate sensors, it is hoped that accurate and comprehensive data will be created to validate existing mathematical models and identify factors that influence the efficiency and quality of pyrolysis products. A better understanding of this process could pave the way for the development of more efficient, environmentally friendly and sustainable biomass pyrolysis technologies in the future.

2. METHOD

The method used in this study is an experimental method based on analyzing heat transfer energy in a pyrolysis system with multistage condenser and temperature data taken by implementing and analyzing dataloggers. In this study, the condenser was designed using a copper coil tube ($\varnothing 12.5 \text{ mm} \times 1,000 \text{ mm}$) with a PVC material shell ($\varnothing 90 \text{ mm} \times 500 \text{ mm}$) for 4 units. To heat the reactor chamber, a high-pressure stove burner with LPG fuel was used.

A fixed bed reactor is a type of reactor in which the basic material is placed in a fixed bed and then heated. This reactor energy can be modeled using (1) [12].

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{Q}{m \cdot c_p} \quad (1)$$

Where:

T : temperature in the reactor ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),

t : time (seconds),

Q : heat rate applied to the reactor ($\text{Watt}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$),

m : mass rate of raw materials in the fixed bed (kg/hour), and

C_p : material heat capacity (Joule/kgK).

The water-cooled spiral condenser cools the bio-oil vapor produced during pyrolysis so that it condenses and becomes liquid. The cooling capacity and heat transfer can be calculated using (2) [13].

$$Q = U \cdot A \cdot \Delta T \quad (2)$$

Where:

Q : heat transferred (Watt/m²K),

U : heat transfer coefficient (Watt/m.K),

A : heat exchange surface area (m²), and

ΔT : temperature difference between steam and cooling medium (°C).

The calculation of heat transfer rates will utilize data obtained from measurements taken throughout the specified experimental timeframe. To achieve accurate and reliable results, it is essential to gather a substantial amount of data, encompassing continuous recordings throughout the entire pyrolysis process. This extensive dataset ensures that the calculations reflect real-time conditions and variations in the reactor, enabling precise modeling of the heat transfer dynamics. By relying on comprehensive experimental data, the analysis will provide a more accurate representation of the thermal behavior within the system, thereby enhancing the validity of the calculated heat transfer rates.

2.1. Temperature datalogger design

In Figure 2 the equipment used in designing the datalogger consists of an Arduino Mega 2560 R3 microcontroller as in Figure 2(a), a temperature sensor used 8 type K thermocouples with working voltage specifications of 3-5 V, temperature measurement range 0-800 °C, accuracy 0.25 °C as in Figure 2(b), and the MAX6675 module as in Figure 2(c). The cooling fluid flow rate is measured using the YF-S201 sensor as in Figure 2(d). Air humidity is measured using a DHT22 sensor, as in Figure 2(e). The non-condensable gas that comes out is measured using the MQ-135 sensor as in Figure 2(f).

Figure 2. Components datalogger system: (a) Arduino mega 2560, (b) module thermocouple Max6675, (c) thermocouple type K, (d) flow sensor YF-S201, (e) humidity and temperature sensor DHT22, and (f) gas sensor MQ135

The system has been meticulously developed following the highly compact wiring diagram design, as illustrated in Figure 3, where each connection has been optimized to minimize cable length and enhance operational efficiency. Additionally, the design was created with careful consideration to avoid potential interference that could arise from overlapping cable paths. This ensures that the sensor measurements are highly precise and accurately reflect real-time conditions observed during the experiment.

Figure 4 displays the computer script specifically developed for the management and monitoring of instruments within the pyrolysis system. This script is tailored to precisely control and record temperature measurements, coolant flow rates, and gas production throughout the experimental process. By enabling real-time data acquisition, it ensures accurate tracking of these parameters, thereby enhancing the analysis and optimization of the multi-stage condenser's performance.

Figure 5. Position of the thermocouple on the system pyrolysis

2.2. Experimental procedure

The raw material, consisting of fallen *Odollam Cerbera* fruit, was sourced from the northern coastal region of Probolinggo district. The initial processing involved size reduction, followed by sun drying for three days. Subsequent drying was conducted in an oven at a temperature of 105 ± 5 °C for three hours. Each process involved weighing 3 kg of the material for three different temperature variations. During the pyrolysis process, key parameters such as temperature, humidity, product gas composition, and coolant flow rate were meticulously recorded. The entire research procedure adhered to the sequence outlined in the flowchart presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Experimental procedure

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Test results temperature data

The results of pyrolysis of *cerbera* fruit with variations in reactor temperature produce pyrolysis products in the form of solids in the form of charcoal and liquids in the form of bio-oil, and the remainder is gas, which cannot be condensed. From Figure 7, it can be seen that the temperature of the reactor experienced a significant increase after the 5th minute and then fluctuated between a temperature of 250 °C and 350 °C. The temperature of the T-in condenser ranges from 87.3 °C to 35.6 °C. Meanwhile, the T-out of the condenser ranges from the lowest value to 22.9 °C. This phenomenon occurs because the initial pyrolysis process requires time to reach the desired operational temperature [15], and after reaching that temperature, temperature fluctuations are caused by variations in raw material supply or complex pyrolysis reaction characteristics. The inlet temperature (T-in) at the first stage condenser also shows quite large fluctuations, although with a lower range.

Figure 7. Temperature changes in reactor and multi-stage condenser

Temperature fluctuations in the reactor, cyclone, and condenser indicate challenges in maintaining stable operational conditions during the pyrolysis process. These temperature fluctuations can affect the efficiency of the pyrolysis process and the resulting product yield. Wide temperature variations can also indicate problems with temperature control and heat transfer in the system. In addition, temperature fluctuations in the condenser can also impact condensation and cooling conditions, which can affect the quality and quantity of the condensed product [16]. Therefore, temperature control and heat transfer in the pyrolysis system need to be considered more carefully to achieve more consistent and optimal results.

3.2. Heat transfer analysis

At high temperatures, as in the case of the highest char yielding temperatures, the dominant chemical reactions include dehydration, depolymerization, decarboxylation, and reduction of complex molecules to simpler compounds. High temperatures destroy chemical bonds in large molecules [17], such as cellulose and lignin [18], which are present in bintaro fruit. This process produces smaller molecules, including hydrocarbon compounds [19]. This reaction is the first step towards the formation of charcoal [20]. This is referred to as depolymerization [21]. Meanwhile, this reaction involves the removal of the carboxyl group (-COOH) from organic compounds as a decarboxylation process which can produce aromatic hydrocarbon compounds [21], which are the main components in charcoal.

The dehydration process also occurs at temperatures of 250-350 °C. The dehydration process removes water molecules from organic compounds, such as cellulose and lignin [22]. This reaction causes an increase in the carbon concentration in the molecular structure [23], which is the main characteristic of charcoal [24]. And finally, there is a molecular reduction process where at a high enough temperature, a reduction reaction occurs where oxygen is released from organic compounds [25]. This results in a higher carbon concentration in the molecular structure, which also contributes to char formation.

3.3. Product of bio-oil

The processes mentioned above, which occur during pyrolysis at temperatures that produce the highest bio-oil, cause changes in the structure and composition of bintaro fruit leading to the formation of

charcoal and bio-oil [26]. Since this chemical reaction is strongly influenced by temperature [27], the proper operational temperature can influence the conversion rate and the final outcome of bio-oil formation in the pyrolysis process as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Product bio-oil in experiment

Based on graphical data, the study reveals that the majority of the bio-oil production was concentrated in condensers C-1 and C-2, with significantly lower yields observed in condensers C-3 and C-4. The substantial disparity in output between the first two condensers and the latter two suggests that the cooling and condensation processes are most efficient in the initial stages, where the temperature gradient and vapor concentration are likely at their peak. Consequently, the effectiveness of the third and fourth condensers is considerably diminished, indicating that future designs of the pyrolysis system may only require the implementation of two condensers to achieve optimal bio-oil recovery. This adjustment could streamline the system, reduce operational complexity [28], and lower costs without compromising the efficiency of bio-oil production.

4. CONCLUSION

To capture and analyze temperature, air humidity, and non-condensable gases throughout the pyrolysis process, a specialized temperature and gas sensor datalogger system was implemented. This system enabled a detailed evaluation of the performance parameters within the multi-stage condenser during the pyrolysis of bintaro fruit waste. The study investigated how variations in reactor temperature and cooling fluid flow rate affected the condenser's efficiency and bio-oil production. The results demonstrated that reactor temperature plays a critical role in determining bio-oil yield, while the temperatures of the smoke entering each condenser and the cooling water significantly influence the composition of the condensates produced at each stage. Future research should focus on optimizing these parameters, potentially varying feedstock composition and condenser configurations, to enhance both yield and quality of bio-oil. The key takeaway is the significant role of advanced sensor technologies in optimizing pyrolysis systems for sustainable biofuel production from biomass waste like bintaro fruit.

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